

Paralympic sports classification and Spatiotemporal parameters of wheelchair racer in male's 100m sprint

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Abstract The purpose of this study is to investigate the difference of spatiotemporal variables(SV) according to sport classification in wheelchair racing 100m final. We used the broadcast to collect 136 data. Based on the Paralympic sport classification(PSC), they were grouped into four groups (male t51~T54). The average speed(S), stroke frequency(SF), stroke length(SL) were calculated using the stroke count(SC) in conjunction with the official time(OT). One-way analysis of variance was performed to compare S, SL, and SF (dependent variables) of the T51, T52, T53 and T54 (independent variables). The results showed that there was significant difference in all variables. The S was higher in the order of lower impaired(t51->t54). Differences in velocity among 4 groups were associated with both SF and SL. We also founded at the wheelchair propulsion strategies of each group. T51 and T52 differed only in SF (not in SL). Whereas T53 and T54 differed only in SL (not in SF). That is, groups with lower impaired indicate A power strategy (the more SL). Current results suggest that spatiotemporal parameters during a 100-m race of wheelchair racer is varied by Paralympic Sports Classification. This will help in training and preventing injuries.

Keywords Wheelchair racing, classification, spatiotemporal variables

Introduction

The most important feature of disabled sports is the classification. The Paralympic Committee classifies players of similar level for fairness purposes. However, the disorder is not clearly defined. Therefore, it is one of the ongoing research projects.

This study analyzed the t51-54 group with sufficient data. The classification of the athletes in this category is affected by limb deficiency, impaired PROM, impaired muscle power, and leg length difference. The lower the number, the more severe the impaired and the more restrictive the movement. These sports disability grades exhibit the following motor characteristics.

T51 has an activity limit corresponding to a player with complete spinal cord injury of nerve c5-6. For propulsion, use elbow flexors and wrist dorsiflexors. Usually, use small handrim. t52 has an activity limit corresponding to a player with complete spinal cord injury of nerve c7-8. Use

shoulders, elbows and wrists for propulsion. You can use gloving skills similar to the following two groups (t53, t54) t53 has a corresponding activity limitation for athletes with nerve t1-7 complete spinal cord injury. These players have normal arm strength and no abdominal and lower spinal muscle mobility. t54 has a corresponding activity limit on athletes with nerve t8-s4 complete spinal cord injury. These athletes will have normal arm strength, which can increase the body strength range from body control to body control. You can change the direction of the wheelchair by applying torso torque while sitting.

This disability rating affects sports performance (Rice, I et al, 2018; Cavedon, V et al, 2015; Hobara, H et al, 2015). The purpose of the 100m sprint is speed. S is the product of SF and SL. (Salo, A, 2011) suggested training in two types, depending on SF and SL. The type of SF is moving fast, so we need access to the nervous system. The type of SL claims to require a strong force and flexibility in its operating range. The study is a sprint study of people without disabilities, but wheelchair users are also considered. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the propulsive characteristics which are indicated by the limitation according to the degree of disability.

Methods

Figure 1. Distribution of subject

Data collected. we used the internet broadcasts for the data collection (paralympic 08', 12', 16' /championship 13',15',17). Based on the finals, 359 people were observed in 48 races. We recorded their PSC, Gender(G), OT, and SC directly by eye. Three observer results were collected to increase the reliability of the data. After data processing, this study analyzed 136 male(t51~t54). The distribution of subjects is shown in Figure1.

Data analysis. S, SL, and SF were calculated by using SC in conjunction with OT. One-way analysis of variance was performed to compare S, SL, and SF (dependent variables) of the T51,

T52, T53 and T54 (independent variables). We also calculated effect sizes. Bonferroni post hoc multiple comparison tests($p=0.125$) were performed if a significant main effect was observed.

Figure 1. Spatiotemporal variables base on classification..

Results

The results showed that there was significant difference in all variables(effect size; S100: 0.96, SI: 0.54, Sf: 0.53). The S100 was higher in the order of lower impaired (m/s; T51: 4.47, T52: 5.57, T53: 6.61, T54: 6.97). Differences in velocity among 4 groups were associated with both Sf and SI. We also founded at the wheelchair propulsion strategies of each group. T51 and T52 differed only in Sf(not in SI). Whereas T53 and T54 differed only in SI(not in Sf). That is, groups with lower impaired indicate A power strategy(the more SI).

Table 1. Spatiotemporal variables base on classification(MEAN \pm SD)

	T51	T52	T53	T54
Average speed(m/s)	4.48 \pm 0.19	5.58 \pm 0.18	6.62 \pm 0.16	6.97 \pm 0.16
Stroke frequency	1.79 \pm 0.12	2.13 \pm 0.17	2.24 \pm 0.14	2.25 \pm 0.17
Stroke length	2.52 \pm 0.19	2.63 \pm 0.18	2.96 \pm 0.22	3.11 \pm 0.26

Conclusion

Current results suggest that spatiotemporal parameters during a 100-m race of wheelchair racer is varied by Paralympic Sports Classification. This will help in training and preventing injuries.

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